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The importance of tutor in Higher Education.

Annotation. Educating young person who are in line with the requirements of the times, willful, thoughtful in all aspects, whose interests are loyal to the idea of creativity is one of the urgent tasks facing educational institutions today. The tutoring system is also aimed at these goals. It is an important form and means of systematic and effective implementation of the educational process in a higher educational institution.

Key words. Education, tutor, young generation, students, problem of youngers.

Аннотация. Воспитание молодежи, отвечающей требованиям времени, волевой, мыслящей во всех отношениях, чьи интересы верны идее творчества, является одной из актуальных задач, стоящих сегодня перед образовательными учреждениями. На эти цели направлена и система тьюторства. Это важная форма и средство планомерной и эффективной реализации образовательного процесса в высшем учебном заведении.

Ключевые слова. Воспитание, тьютор, молодое поколение, студенты, проблема студенты.

Annotatsiya. Zamon talabiga mos, irodali, har tomonlama tafakkurli, qiziqishi bunyodkorlik g'oyasiga sodiq yoshlarni tarbiyalash bugungi kunda ta'lim muassasalari oldida turgan dolzarb vazifalardan biridir. Tyutorlik tizimi ham ana shu maqsadlarga qaratilgan. Bu oliy ta'lim muassasasida o'quv jarayonini tizimli va samarali amalga oshirishning muhim shakli va vositasidir.

Kalit so'zlar. Ta'lim, tarbiyachi, yosh avlod, talabalar, yoshlar muammosi

A person is not born spiritually and morally rich, therefore, spiritual and moral education occupies a leading place in the upbringing of the young generation. The task of higher education is not only to train specialists, but also to educate a mature and worthy generation in all respects, which will determine the present and future of our country. For this reason, the activity of tutors was launched in higher education at the initiative of our honorable president.

Educating young person who are in line with the requirements of the times, willful, thoughtful in all aspects, whose interests are loyal to the idea of creativity is one of the urgent tasks facing educational institutions today.

The tutoring system is also aimed at these goals. It is an important form and means of systematic and effective implementation of the educational process in a higher educational institution. A tutor is a pedagogue who helps students' personal development, worthy participation in competitions and Olympiads at the educational institution, republican and international level, as well as meaningful spending of their free time. and studies its shortcomings and deals with finding a comprehensive solution to them.

A student can have as little as just over 2 hours as their leisure time. This limits the activities of most students to studying, self-improvement, recreational activities, surfing the internet, making use of smartphones, and spending time with their family and friends. Students seldom indulge in exercises owing to the constrained hours and the availability of equipment. But they have to more fun activity in their leisure time. Totally we request for students hang out with friends in historical places. Such as Khiva, Samarqand and Bukhara. These places change their minds for their country.

- Traveling

This is often the highlight of a student's leisure hours though it's only possible during semester breaks. They go on vacation and experience foreign and new cultures. Most academic institutions sometimes have their scholars go on field trips.

- Sports

During their leisure hours, students also indulge in recreational sports activities. They take on the role of either a participant or a spectator. Sports such as soccer, basketball, football, and hockey are popular activities scholars indulge in during their leisure time.

In conclusion it depends on student character and feelings, we do not force them to do something, but we request them their choice more important for us.